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SHORT-PAPER

Modelling Musical Meaning: A Semantically Enriched Corpus from Nineteenth-Century Spanish Music Lexicons

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Abstract

This paper presents work in progress within the *Spanish Lexicon and Ontology of Music* (LexiMus) Subproject 2 (SP2), aimed at constructing a semantically enriched corpus from nineteenth-century Spanish music dictionaries. By converting historical lexicographic sources (ca. 1850–1920) into structured data, the project enables digital representation, querying, and comparative analysis of musical concepts. The corpus integrates ontological modelling (subject–predicate–object triples) and manual annotation of conceptual relations, organising musical knowledge into categories such as sound entities, musical forms, performance practices, and reception. Through semantic enrichment, the system supports complex SPARQL queries and enables diachronic analysis of terminological and conceptual changes. We illustrate this approach through a case study on the term *acorde* (chord) in dictionaries by Carlos José Melcior (1859), María Luisa Lacal (1899), and Jaime Pahissa (1929), highlighting semantic variations across time. LexiMus contributes to digital musicology by bridging historical music discourse and semantic web technologies, facilitating organised navigation through concepts, alignment with contemporary music ontologies, and potential inclusion in digital libraries.

Keywords

Digital musicology, Semantic enrichment, Historical lexicons, Ontological modelling, Nineteenth-century music theory

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1 Introduction

This paper presents ongoing results from LexiMus SP2, which models Spanish music dictionaries (1850–1920) as structured semantic corpora. LexiMus SP2 operates at the intersection of three key domains: (1) the digital representation of historical musical knowledge, (2) the relationship between semantic structures and historically situated knowledge, and (3) the metarepresentation of music theory discourse. Initiatives such as the Music Ontology [13] and the Polifonia Ontology Network [12] have proposed domain ontologies that aims at integrating heterogeneous music-related datasets. The HaMSE Ontology, in turn, provides a flexible framework to align melodic, harmonic, and emotional descriptors in musicological analysis [11].

LexiMus SP2 adopts a bottom-up strategy rooted in historical sources. It models not only musical concepts but also their historical definitions, tracing the ways in which knowledge was classified, expressed, and hierarchised in 19th-century lexicographic discourse. In doing so, it embraces the asymmetries and ambiguities found in those texts rather than reducing them to uniform categories. Rather than replacing existing models, however, it provides a diachronic and historically grounded account of musical concepts—one that may support future mappings to broader semantic frameworks such as those proposed by Polifonia or HaMSE.

This approach is conceptually aligned with projects such as EncycNet [14], which semantically model historical encyclopaedias to study the evolution of knowledge representations over time. From this perspective, LexiMus contributes a metaontological and historiographical layer that can complement universal or modular domain ontologies. Ultimately, LexiMus provides not only a structured dataset but also a methodological framework for exploring how musical thought was lexically and conceptually articulated in the past.

2 Corpus Sources

The Spanish tradition of music lexicography in the 19th century was limited in number but significant, beginning in the mid-1800s with works like Antonio Fargas [17], Carlos José Melcior [7], and José Parada [16], followed by Pedrell’s technical dictionary [10], and culminating in comprehensive compilations such as Luisa Lacal’s *Diccionario de música, técnico, histórico, bio-bibliográfico* [4]. Jaime Pahissa’s *Diccionario de la música ilustrado* [9] extended this ‘tradition’ [8] into the twentieth century. *LexiMus* builds upon this legacy by bringing such texts into the digital environment and by semantically enriching them—namely, by augmenting each entry with formalised meaning.

3 Methods: Ontology-Based Modelling of Historical Music Terminology

Existing research on Spanish musical lexicographical sources has largely followed traditional methodologies, relying on close reading and historical-contextual analysis of dictionaries, their compilation processes, and their editorial frameworks [5, 6, 8, 15]. To our knowledge, only one digital lexicographic project focused on music demonstrates implicit ontological potential—namely, Thomas Gloning’s *Historisches Vokabular des Jazz* [2]. Although it organises vocabulary through semantic-functional categories and complex systems of descriptors, it does not adopt formal ontological frameworks or semantic web technologies such as RDF or OWL, as proposed in *LexiMus* [1].

To achieve semantic enrichment, our subproject adopts an ontoterminological modelling approach that bridges traditional terminology (i.e., dictionary entries and definitions) with formal ontology (i.e., concepts and relationships expressed in a knowledge graph—a structured network of interlinked concepts). Each dictionary entry will be encoded in TEI and modelled as a set of RDF triples (subject–predicate–object statements used to represent knowledge in semantic web standards), capturing its key semantic relationships [1].

For example, a definition can be represented as a triple like (‘Chord’ – isDefinedAs – ‘simultaneous combination of notes’), and cross-references or attributes as additional triples (e.g., ‘Chord’ – hasProperty – ‘harmonious sound’). In practice, this approach requires carefully identifying entities (things or concepts), relationships (semantic links between them), and properties (attributes or characteristics) in the textual definitions and commentary of each source. Domain experts (i.e., the members of the research team) manually segment the dictionary texts into semantic units: the main term (entity), the type of relation (e.g., ‘is a kind of’, ‘is defined as’, ‘requires’), and the target concept or value. These are initially tabulated using spreadsheets (Excel) as an intermediate step, prior to formal encoding in Protégé for ontology management and reasoning. Each triple has been further classified by its type: for instance, whether it denotes an object property (a relation between two concepts), a data property (a link between a concept and a literal value or textual note), or a definitional statement (a sentence expressing a term’s meaning).

The workflow for modelling each dictionary thus involves digitisation and OCR, semi-automated annotation of terms and relations (recorded in a structured format like Excel or a database), reconciliation of those terms with a growing central ontology, and validation of the triples. Throughout the process, consistency checks and reasoning tools (software that infers implicit knowledge and detects logical contradictions) ensure that the ontology remains logically coherent (e.g., no contradictory class hierarchies) despite integrating heterogeneous sources. By the end of the methods pipeline, the project produces a structured, interlinked dataset of musical concepts as described by historical sources, ready for analysis and comparison. Our corpus provides a diachronic layer (tracking changes over time) that may support mappings to broader ontologies such as PON. In validating our model, we have also made use—albeit implicitly—of competency questions [3] (queries used to test whether an ontology can answer the kinds of questions it

was designed for), especially in the modelling of central terms like *acorde*, to ensure its adequacy for answering historically situated research queries, acknowledging thus the differences in concepts that stem from local history.

4 Ontological Structure of Melcior’s Dictionary

Our proposed structuring of Melcior’s dictionary [7] is based on a hierarchical organisation of musical knowledge into broad conceptual categories, designed to reflect both the technical and the cultural-historical dimensions of the terms that appear in 19th-century dictionaries (Figure 1). At the core of the system lies the domain *Music*, which branches into two primary dimensions: on the one hand, the artistic-technical domain; on the other, the historical-cultural traditions in which such knowledge is embedded. This dual structure enables the simultaneous representation of both the internal properties of musical objects and the contexts of their use, transmission, and evolution. Within the artistic-technical dimension, the model includes categories ranging from basic sound materials (such as *sound*, *note*, *acoustic interval*) to more complex musical entities like *chord*, *modulation*, *melody*, and *musical phrase*. It also incorporates musical processes (*compose*, *sing*, *improvise*), musical objects (*cantata*, *aria*, *hymn*), expressive resources (*dynamics*, *agogics*, *ornamentation*), and systematic domains such as *harmony* and *counterpoint*. The complementary historical dimension integrates cultural traditions and links terms to their original or received contexts. A transversal layer of semantic relationships is also included to disambiguate polysemous terms (such as *interval*, *key*, or *cadence*), which is essential for building a coherent ontological model of historical musical knowledge.

This proposed structure is intended to reflect the organisation of musical knowledge as it appeared in European scholarly sources around 1859, particularly in Melcior’s dictionary. For instance, the artistic-technical dimension combines materials, actions, and bodies of knowledge—echoing the nineteenth-century understanding of music as simultaneously art, craft, and science. Likewise, the category *musical object* encompasses complete works, fragments, and didactic pieces, mirroring the undifferentiated treatment common in historical sources. Categories such as *expression* and *execution* are retained to reflect the interpretive tension between rule and gesture characteristic of the period, while *performative events* are modelled as temporally situated instances without isolating subcategories of context—consistent with how such contexts are embedded in the lexicon in terms like *serenata* or *velada*.

Voice types provide another example of this historically grounded modelling. In our proposed ontology, human voices (such as tenor, soprano, bass, etc.) are not modelled as independent acoustic entities or as organological equivalents to musical instruments; rather, they are treated as inherent attributes of the musical agents who emit them. Definitions like ‘Tenor: a certain timbre of the human voice and the second in its order’ reveal that voice is characterised primarily by its timbral quality—and placed within a normative functional hierarchy—rather than by a quantifiable range. Thus, voices must be understood as embodied semantic categories, socially constructed and functionally inseparable from the musical agent. Similarly, we deliberately refrain from incorporating modern categories such as ‘musical genre’ or ‘form’ as independent classes.

In Melcior's dictionary, the term 'genre' [*género*] has a technical meaning that refers to ancient categories (diatonic, chromatic, and enharmonic) rather than to the classification of musical works by structure, function, or usage (e.g., sonata, mass, dance, march).

```

1 {
2   "Music": {
3     "definition": "General domain encompassing the practices,
4     ↳ objects, knowledge, and phenomena related to the organization
5     ↳ of sound in the cultivated European sphere around 1859.",
6     "Artistic and Technical Dimension": {
7       "definition": "Grouping of all components that constitute
8       ↳ musical practice understood as both art and science.",
9       "Basic Sound Materials": "Primary physical elements from which
10      ↳ music is organized.",
11      "Structured Musical Entities": "Regulated combinations of basic
12      ↳ sound materials, organized through musical knowledge.",
13      "Discursive Units": "Organized fragments of musical discourse,
14      ↳ which may be part of a musical object or, exceptionally,
15      ↳ constitute one if self-sufficient.",
16      "Expression and Performance": "Modes of interpretation that
17      ↳ affect the tempo, intensity, and articulation of musical
18      ↳ discourse.",
19      "Musical Knowledge": "Sets of rules guiding the organization of
20      ↳ materials, structured musical entities, and discursive
21      ↳ units, as well as the overcoming of difficulties in
22      ↳ performance.",
23      "Musical Activities": "Actions through which human agents
24      ↳ produce or interpret music.",
25      "Musical Agents": "Human agents who carry out actions leading to
26      ↳ the production, performance, or dissemination of music.",
27      "Musical Objects": "Complete and autonomous discursive
28      ↳ constructions that integrate materials, entities, and units
29      ↳ into a performable or notated work.",
30      "Sound-Producing Musical Objects": "Physical objects that
31      ↳ produce sound with musical intent, such as musical
32      ↳ instruments and their components.",
33      "Performance and Support Objects": "Physical objects necessary
34      ↳ for or aiding musical performance, as well as the material
35      ↳ means for fixing and transmitting music.",
36      "Musical Notation": "Systems for fixing and transmitting
37      ↳ music.",
38      "Performative Events": "Spatiotemporal instances in which music
39      ↳ is actualized through performance.",
40      "Perception and Reception": "Processes of listening, judgment,
41      ↳ and response to the musical experience."
42    },
43    "Historical and Linguistic Dimension": {
44      "definition": "Grouping of categories related to terminological
45      ↳ tradition, and the historical, cultural, and semantic
46      ↳ contexts in which musical practice is embedded.",
47      "Sources of Authority": "Key references that serve as a basis
48      ↳ for the definition of musical terms.",
49      "Historical Entities": "Individuals, private organizations, or
50      ↳ institutions mediating musical practice.",
51      "Cultural and Historical Traditions": "Geographical and
52      ↳ historical contexts in which music developed with
53      ↳ distinctive features.",
54      "Loanwords": "Musical terms originating from other languages
55      ↳ that have been adopted in the European musical context.",
56      "Semantic Relations and Coreference": "Handling of polysemy and
57      ↳ meaning relations among musical terms."
58    }
59  }
60 }

```

Figure 1: Ontological structure of musical knowledge in Carlos José Melcior's *Diccionario Enciclopédico de la Música* (1859).

5 Case Study: Modelling 'Acorde' (Chord) in Three Dictionaries

A representative example of LexiMus's approach is the term *acorde* (chord), as defined by Melcior, Lcal, and Pahissa. Their definitions and emphases reflect the historical evolution of music theory and terminology—an evolution that the ontological model must be capable of accommodating. Below, we summarise each source's treatment of *acorde* and examine how it is semantically represented in the form of triples extracted and normalised using structured Excel tables. Melcior adopts an acoustic-perceptual perspective in which the chord is conceived as a resonant entity, defined by properties such as :hasProperty Resonance (:tienePropiedad Resonancia) or :perceivedAs Pleasant (:percibidoComo Agradable), thereby articulating an ontology closely aligned with the physics of sound. Lcal privileges a logical-formal framework, grounded in structural classifications such as 'direct order' or 'dissonant species', conceptualising the chord as a combinatorial object composed of intervals. Pahissa, by contrast, works within a historical-functional epistemology, understanding chords as constructs that vary across time, usage, and theoretical tradition. His model employs relations such as :equivalentInHistoricalTreatisesTo (:esEquivalenteEnTratadosHistóricosA) or :variesAccordingToPeriod (:variaSegunEpoca). A clear example of this divergence is the treatment of the property :perceivedAs (:percibidoComo), which illustrates the differences between acoustic-normative, structural, and cultural models. Melcior employs this property extensively and with semantic precision, establishing clear normative conditions linked to auditory perception (Figure 2). Lcal, though less prolific, uses this property to underscore structural effects, employing rhetorical imagery (Figure 3). Pahissa, who defines *chord* as a 'composite sonority resulting from the coordinated and simultaneous combination of several different sounds' (*Sonoridad compuesta que resulta de la unión coordinada y simultánea de varios sonidos diferentes*), does not at any point address perceptual considerations.

```

1 Dissonant_Chord :perceivedAs Tense
2 (Acorde_Disonante :percibidoComo Tenso)
3 Dissonant_Chord :perceivedIfUnpreparedAs Unbearable
4 (Acorde_Disonante :percibidoSiNoSePreparaComo Insoportable)
5 Diminished_Seventh_Chord :perceivedAs Sweet
6 (Acorde_Séptima_Diminuta :percibidoComo Dulce)
7

```

Figure 2: Examples of semantic triples from Melcior's *Diccionario Enciclopédico de la Música* related to auditory perception.

```

1 Diminished_Dissonant_Chord :perceivedAs Sweet
2 (Acorde_disonante_diminuto :percibidoComo Dulce)
3 Consonant_Chord_Without_Link :perceivedAs
4 ↳ Isolated_words_in_the_discourse
5 (Acorde_Consonante_Sin_Enlace :percibidoComo
6 ↳ Palabras_sueltas_en_el_discurso)
7

```

Figure 3: Examples of semantic triples from Lcal's *Diccionario de la Música* linking structure and perception.

The comparison among these dictionaries reveals the plurality of conceptual frameworks through which harmony has historically been theorised. This diversity is not a limitation for semantic integration but rather a valuable resource: by uncovering how each tradition selects, prioritises, and articulates properties such as `:perceivedAs` (`:percibidoComo`), `:resolvesTo` (`:seResuelveEn`), or `:composedOf` (`:compuestoPor`), the doctrinal density of musical definitions becomes visible. In this sense, the analysis of RDF triples serves not only as a tool for data interoperability, but also as a critical method for exposing the ontological and epistemological assumptions embedded in each theoretical corpus.

6 Toward a Global Ontological Model: Integration and Inference

We acknowledge differences in conceptualisation by modelling them either as optional properties of a concept or as related sub-concepts (e.g., a subclass `TriadicChord` reflecting Melcior’s implicit assumptions). The process of aligning multiple dictionaries raises questions of equivalence—such as whether the *acorde* of 1859 is the same as that of 1899. `LexiMus` handles such cases by distinguishing between core concepts and source-specific variants. When meanings differ significantly, they are modelled as separate but linked entities using relations like `historicalSuccessorOf` or `broaderThan`. In the case of *acorde*, however, the meanings are layered rather than contradictory. We represent these layers as properties: for instance, a data property `historical_minimum_components` might be assigned values like `'3 (Melcior1859)'` and `'2 (Lacal1899)'`.

This structure enables SPARQL queries and automated reasoning. The system can infer, for example, that Melcior’s definition presupposes a third tone in a chord, or that all chords are a subclass of `Simultaneous_Sonorous_Event`, which itself implies at least two notes. While advanced inferences—like deducing an implicit third note in a dyad—may exceed OWL’s native capabilities, they may be realised with rule extensions. Temporal properties (e.g., `earliestMention = 14th century`) further allow for queries like ‘Which concepts first emerged in the 14th century?’ or ‘Which properties of Chord persist across 1859, 1899, and 1929?’

Finally, the global model links historical concepts to external standards (e.g., Wikidata, CIDOC CRM, MIMO), bridging 19th-century lexicography and contemporary knowledge structures. This not only supports diachronic comparison—such as how the term *sonata* evolves—but also makes the `LexiMus` corpus interoperable with broader cultural heritage data, enabling cross-domain queries across music theory, lexicography, and historiography.

7 Conclusion and Future Work

In summary, building the global ontology from local models involves aligning overlapping concepts and enriching them where individual sources provide additional detail. This semantic integration allows for formal comparison of definitions, identification of implicit assumptions, and inferencing beyond what was possible from the original texts. The result is a machine-actionable representation of nineteenth-century music theory as encoded in historical dictionaries.

Future work will focus on the introduction of automation in the modelling process using tools such as OpenRefine for orthographic normalisation, combined with structured prompts that guide language models in TEI/XML annotation and RDF extraction. Expert validation remains essential to preserve historical nuance, whilst these pipelines aim to ensure both precision and scalability. Technically, the ontology will be implemented in OWL/RDF and hosted in a hybrid architecture combining a triplestore and a relational database, enabling both semantic queries and lexical access. Integration with a semantic reasoner and search index will further support advanced navigation and interoperability with digital libraries and musicological platforms.

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